

SCALIBUR

LEADING A REVOLUTION
IN BIOWASTE RECYCLING

Project videos

Deliverable 9.2

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Deliverable fact sheet

Document name	D9.2 Project videos	
Responsible partner	Greenovate! Europe	
Deliverable number	9.2	
Due date of deliverable	30 April 2020	
Actual submission date		
Version	1	
Authors	James Ling (G!E)	
Reviewers	Martin Stroleny (G!E)	
Work package no.	9	
Work package title	Communication, Dissemination and Awareness raising	
Work package leader	Greenovate! Europe	
Work package participants	All partners	
Dissemination level (please select one)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	PU Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP Restricted to other programme participants, including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nature of the deliverable (please select one)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	R Report	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	D Demonstrator	<input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	W Websites, patents filing, etc	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	O Other	<input type="checkbox"/>

ABSTRACT

As part of the communication activities in Work Package 9, Greenovate! Europe has produced three animated videos. The subject of the videos is the three valorisation lines being demonstrated in SCALIBUR, for the conversion of biowaste into added value products.

The objective of the 3 videos is to introduce stakeholders to the valorisation processes, providing a short, visually appealing, 'trailer' to raise interest in the processes under development. The videos have been designed to address multiple stakeholders, including municipalities, the R&D community and also citizens.

The videos have been published on the SCALIBUR youtube channel, and the files have been made available to project partners for use at conferences and exhibitions. Whenever possible the videos should be published next to a link to the relevant page on the SCALIBUR project website, where interested parties can access additional information and contact the responsible SCALIBUR partner.

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INTRODUCTION

Dissemination and awareness activities are a core part of the SCALIBUR project and will maximise the opportunities for SCALIBUR results to be used and exploited at European level after the project's end.

Videos are a very effective way to communicate complex topics, and an appealing way to raise awareness. In the SCALIBUR project three videos are planned to visualise the three valorisation lines being demonstrated for the conversion of biowaste into added value products.

1 SUBJECT AND CONTENT

The subject and structure of the videos has been established in the description of action:

a set of 3 one-minute animated videos will be produced to raise awareness on the 3 main valorisation lines

Each video shows the whole chain – from waste disposal, to conversion and transformation into new products - in a condensed form. By showing the whole cycle we hope to make it understandable for all viewers. The style is colourful and also human centred, to make it both attractive and relatable.

The storyboard for each video is shown below.

1.1 Household waste valorisation line (video 1)

The video begins with a citizen disposing of their food waste at home.

The next screen highlights the scale of food waste produced, and explains why this is a problem for cities.

The next frames introduce the objective of SCALIBUR – to turn waste into a resource for added value bio-products.

The processes to convert household biowaste into products is briefly shown. This aspect was agreed with technical partners to ensure a level of realism and accuracy.

The products under development are shown. Also how they will be used.

By way of conclusion it is explained how these processes can contribute to a circular bioeconomy in cities and the EU as a whole.

A final call to action asks interested viewers to visit the project website to find out more detailed information.

All partner logos are shown and EU funding is acknowledged on the last frame.

1.2 HORECA and retail waste valorisation line (video 2)

The video begins in a restaurant to emphasise that this process relates to HORECA and retail waste.

The next screen highlights the scale of food waste produced, and explains why this is a problem for cities.

The next frames introduce the objective of SCALIBUR – to turn waste into a resource for added value bio-products

The processes to convert HORECA biowaste into products is briefly shown. This aspect was agreed with technical partners to ensure a level of realism and accuracy.

An example of the final products is shown.

By way of conclusion it is explained how these processes can contribute to a circular bioeconomy in cities and the EU as a whole.

A final call to action asks interested viewers to visit the project website to find out more detailed information.

All partner logos are shown and EU funding is acknowledged on the last frame.

1.3 Sewage sludge valorisation line (video 3)

The video begins with a short explanation of what is 'sewage sludge' and where it comes from.

The next frames introduce the objective of SCALIBUR – to turn waste into a resource for added value bio-products

First the process being developed by Aqualia is briefly shown and described. Sample products are shown.

This is followed by the process from Wetsus, also showing the end product.

By way of conclusion it is explained how these processes can contribute to a circular bioeconomy in cities and the EU as a whole.

A final call to action asks interested viewers to visit the project website to find out more detailed information.

All partner logos are shown and EU funding is acknowledged on the last frame.

2 DISTRIBUTION

The videos have initially been published on the SCALIBUR youtube channel:

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCRWceL7F0gWIDNSbGAM2WOW>

They will be featured on the Greenovate! Europe youtube channel, and other partners will be asked to feature them on their channels or playlists.

Youtube gives the videos a permanent home which will endure beyond the project lifetime.

It also makes it easy to embed the videos into other sites.

The videos will be featured prominently on the SCALIBUR project website and social media channels.

The original video files will also be made available to partners, who will be encouraged to use them at events and exhibitions.

SCALIBUR (Scalable technologies for bio-urban waste recovery) brings together a unique blend of organisations and expertise, led by **ITENE Packaging, Transport & Logistics Research Center**. The project began in November 2018 and will run for four years.

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